

Has infinity come to an end in mathematics?

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Abstract. This paper shows how the infinity of natural numbers can produce a real contradiction.

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1 Finite quantity of natural numbers

Theorem 1.1. *The set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ of non-zero natural numbers, constructed using the decimal number system, can only have a finite number of elements.*

Proof. First let's assume that the decimal numerical system is capable of representing every natural number, without any limit. This allows us to write the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ in the following way:

$$\mathbb{N}_{>0} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots\}$$

Let's now take the set P consisting of the even numbers contained within the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ just defined:

$$P = \{2, 4, 6, 8, \dots\} \subset \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

and the set D consisting of the odd numbers always contained within the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$:

$$D = \{1, 3, 5, 7, \dots\} \subset \mathbb{N}_{>0}$$

Remembering that the following ordinal ω is the cardinal number of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$:

$$\omega = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$$

we can construct the following application $h: \omega \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{>0}$

$$\begin{aligned}h(0) &= 2 \\h(1) &= 4 \\h(2) &= 6 \\h(3) &= 8 \\&\dots\end{aligned}$$

that follows the rule:

$$h(n) = 2 \cdot (n + 1) \quad \forall n \in \omega$$

Having considered the decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, the application h will be valid for all the elements of the ordinal ω and for all the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$ that are even numbers, and therefore also for all the elements of its proper subset P , none excluded.

This means that the application h is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , and therefore it will be true that:

$$\begin{aligned}\forall x \in \omega \exists! p \in P : (x, p) \in h \\ \forall p \in P \exists! x \in \omega : (x, p) \in h\end{aligned}$$

And we can represent the application h in the following way:

$$h = \{(0, 2), (1, 4), (2, 6), (3, 8), \dots, (n, 2 \cdot (n + 1)), \dots\}$$

with pairs that have as left element a different element of the ordinal ω and as right element a different element of the set P , and that taken together exhaust both the elements of one and the elements of the other.

Let's now take the following application $f: \omega \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{>0}$

$$\begin{aligned}f(0) &= 1 \\f(1) &= 2 \\f(2) &= 3 \\f(3) &= 4 \\&\dots\end{aligned}$$

that follows the rule:

$$f(n) = n + 1 \quad \forall n \in \omega$$

Having considered the decimal numerical system capable of representing every

natural number, without any limit, the application f will be valid for all the elements of the ordinal ω and for all the elements of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, none excluded.

This means that the application f is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, and therefore it will be true that:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \exists! n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0} : (x, n) \in f \\ \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0} \exists! x \in \omega : (x, n) \in f \end{aligned}$$

And we can represent the application f in the following way:

$$f = \{(0, 1), (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4), \dots, (n, n + 1), \dots\}$$

with pairs that have as left element a different element of the ordinal ω and as right element a different element of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, and that taken together exhaust both the elements of one and the elements of the other.

We call even and odd pairs those that have respectively an even or odd number on the right. And let's take the first even pair of the application f :

$$(1, 2)$$

We know that the element on its left, in this case equal to 1, is present on the left only in this pair of the application f and being an element of the ordinal ω will be present on the left also in a single pair of the application h . In the same way we know that the element to its right, in this case equal to 2, will be present on the right only in this pair of the application f and being an element of the set P will be present on the right also in a single pair of the application h .

Since the pairs just identified are two and coincide with the following:

$$(0, 2), (1, 4)$$

all we have to do is construct an application h_1 that has the same pairs as the application h except for the two just identified, in place of which we will take the following two that have the same right elements, but have the left elements exchanged between them:

$$(1, 2), (0, 4)$$

so that one of them ends up coinciding with the first even pair of the application f .

Because the application h is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , the application h_1 will also be bijective considering that it has the same pairs, with the sole exception of two pairs which, however, have the same elements

as the two original pairs. But even more important: the application h_1 thus constructed will contain the first even pair of the application f :

$$h_1 = \{(1, 2), (0, 4), (2, 6), (3, 8), \dots\}$$

Note that if the value element 1 of the ordinal ω and the value element 2 of the set P had been part of only one pair of the application h , it would have been sufficient to construct an application h_1 identical to the application h . Such an application h_1 would have been in fact both bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P and able to have inside it the first even pair of the application f .

Let's now take the second even pair of the application f :

$$(3,4)$$

We know that the element on its left, in this case equal to 3, is present on the left only in this pair of the application f and being an element of the ordinal ω will be present on the left also in a single pair of the application h_1 . In the same way we know that the element to its right, in this case equal to 4, will be present on the right only in this pair of the application f and being an element of the set P will be present on the right also in a single pair of the application h_1 .

Since the pairs just identified are two and coincide with the following:

$$(3,8),(0,4)$$

all we have to do is construct an application h_2 that has the same pairs as the application h_1 except for the two just identified, in place of which we will take the following two that have the same right elements, but have the left elements exchanged between them:

$$(0,8),(3,4)$$

so that one of them ends up coinciding with the second even pair of the application f .

Because the application h_1 is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , the application h_2 will also be bijective considering that it has the same pairs, with the sole exception of two pairs which, however, have the same elements as the two original pairs. But even more important: the application h_2 thus constructed will contain the second even pair of the application f , and all other even pairs of the application f already contained in the application h_1 , in this

case the first one:

$$h_2 = \{(1, 2), (3, 4), (2, 6), (0, 8), \dots\}$$

This is because the only pairs of the application h_1 that change in the application h_2 are those with an element on the right or left in common with the even pair of the application f that determined those changes. And we know that such an even pair cannot have any element on the left and right in common with any other even pair of that same application.

Note that if the value element 3 of the ordinal ω and the value element 4 of the set P had been part of only one pair of the application h_1 , it would have been sufficient to construct an application h_2 identical to the application h_1 . Such an application h_2 would have been in fact both bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P and able to have inside it the first two even pairs of the application f .

The procedure that led us from the application h_1 to the following h_2 can be repeated for each successive even pair of the application f , obtaining new applications h_3, h_4, h_5, \dots always bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , and having in common with the application f gradually the first three, four, five \dots even pairs.

Since we have considered the decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, there cannot be any even pair of the application f that can escape from this procedure. This means that it will be possible to construct also the application h_∞ , always bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , consisting of all and only the even pairs of the application f .

To sum it up we have an application h_∞ defined by all and only even pairs of the application f :

$$h_\infty = \{(x - 1, x) : x \in P\}$$

which is certainly existing because it is obtained through valid operations made on applications: h, h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots which in turn exist, and is constructed in such a way as to be bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P . And it is precisely this last property that generates a contradiction.

In fact, if the application h_∞ is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set P , the pairs of which it is composed will be able to exhaust all the elements of the set P but also all the elements of the ordinal ω . The problem is that these pairs are also present in the application f , and if they exhaust all the elements of the ordinal ω there should be no other distinct elements of the ordinal ω within the application f that can match the odd numbers of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$, as it happens instead.

Another way to identify the same contradiction is to observe that the even

pairs of the application f do not exhaust all the elements of the ordinal ω , having to use part of these elements to match them to the odd numbers of the set $\mathbb{N}_{>0}$. The problem is that the application h_∞ is constituted with only the even pairs of the application f and if these do not exhaust all the elements of the ordinal ω , then also the application h_∞ should not be able to do so, as it happens instead.

Since this contradiction occurs in an inevitably way starting from the hypothesis that the decimal numerical system is capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, we are forced to consider this hypothesis false.

This means that if we want to avoid this contradiction, there must be at least one natural number that cannot be represented by the decimal numerical system. Which number will limit those that can be represented by such a system to the only ones that precede it, which will therefore be finite. □

2 New prospects in mathematics

In the margin of this demonstration we can briefly mention that if the non-zero natural numbers are finite, the integer numbers that are the same with the addition of their opposites and zero must also be finite. Moreover, if we proceed in a completely specular way to what we have just seen, we can demonstrate that even the rational and irrational numbers that can be represented by the decimal numerical system must be finite.

Finally, applying the procedure adopted here also in the axiomatic set theory, we immediately come to the conclusion that natural numbers, having to be finite, cannot be constructed with Peano axioms.